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**The Buddhist Cosmopolis:
Universal Welfare, Universal Outreach,
Universal Message**

Peter SKILLING

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The Buddhist Cosmopolis: Universal Welfare, Universal Outreach, Universal Message¹

Peter SKILLING

Preamble

Developed or mature Buddhist texts present Śākyamuni as a universal teacher with a universal message. He achieved awakening for the welfare of the world and for the benefit of all sentient beings. He founded a monastic order – the ‘*saṃgha* of the four quarters’² – that was open to all walks of life, male and female. The Master’s founding principles inspired a policy of universal outreach grounded in compassion, which exerted a strong influence on the evolution of Buddhist thought. It seems possible that the universalization of the Dharma encouraged the universalization of the Buddha: that metaphysics and Buddhology marched hand in hand through a constantly expanding universe, ultimately turning inward to discover and proclaim that ‘all beings possess Buddha-nature’. At the same time, this Buddha was omniscient, and his realizations and his teachings had to reflect this. The development of *Abhidharma* and *Prajñāpāramitā* testify to this process.

The idea of ‘Buddhist universalism’ is difficult. Its meaning is not immediately transparent. If it causes us to think, this may be an advantage in an age that expects intellectual discourse to be ‘user friendly’ to the point that it is reduced to bland and fuzzy platitudes. What aspect of this multivalent term, universalism, is relevant? ‘Universal History’ has been around for four hundred years or more, and I am not convinced that it has made much progress. Many, including even Voltaire, have searched for a universal religion, and the search continues; Sylvain Lévi wrote a perceptive essay on ‘Universal religions and local religions’, summarized as on the ‘*caractères arbitraires des classifications des religions au regard de leur développement et de leurs conséquences historiques, géographiques et sociales*’.³ The second half of the nineteenth century saw a series of ‘Expositions Universelles’, variously called ‘World Fair’ or ‘Weltausstellung’ in other languages, but ‘International Fairs from 1928 onwards’.⁴ The Axial Age came and went, but is still remembered, or memorialized, by bands of enthusiasts. Universal projects tend to be sabotaged by specifics and by the relentless spinning of the wheels of time.

My original title, ‘Building the Buddhist cosmopolis: Language, translation, writing and the universal message of the Buddha’ – was unpardonably cumbersome. I have always felt that ‘cosmopolis’ is a nice and friendly word – until I realized that I might unwittingly give the impression that I intend to launch a critique of or an addendum to the famous cosmopolises of Sheldon Pollack and his school. But I have no such agenda: my subject is not the or any Sanskrit cosmopolis, or in contradistinction this or that vernacular cosmopolis. My subject, broadly speaking, is Buddhist communities that were non-language-exclusive. These were communities of shared knowledge and shared languages – using, according to the *Vimalaprabhā Laghukālacakratantrarājā-ṭīkā*, as many as ninety-six languages,⁵ and theirs was a ‘*universalisme avant la lettre*’. Cosmopolitanism is opposed to exclusivism and monoculturism, and diversity is one of the themes of this paper. In any case, my final title is ‘The Buddhist cosmopolis: universal benefit, universal outreach, universal message’. I examine early Indian Buddhist records to see what they can tell us about universalism. I look at texts and inscriptions in Prakrits like Pāli, Gāndhārī, and that used at Kanaganahalli, in Hybrid Sanskrits, and in Sanskrit.⁶

Universal Others, Other Universals

Whether ‘universalism’ in the senses used in the west, especially in Christianity, corresponds to any core concept or concepts in ancient Buddhist thought is doubtful – I find it hard to think of any precise equivalents. The philosophical dialectics and the historical dynamics of contemporary universalism belong to a very ‘other’, non-theological and even non-metaphysical terrain than that of early Buddhism. Concepts integral to western religion and modern religious studies are simply absent in Buddhism. Rather than highlight them, comparative studies challenge them, along with a host of binary and conceptual categories.

Try as I might, I have been unable to find any exact equivalent in ancient Buddhist thought or literature for ‘universal’ or ‘universalism’ in the senses used in the west or even in global modernism. Universal has multiple pre-modern, modern, and post-modern values. The pre-modern value was steeped in the doctrines of the Church – that is, of the Catholic or Universal Church.⁷ The Enlightenment ushered in new universalisms, in a search for universal values on the physical, moral, and, ultimately, the political planes.⁸ In the modern period, the abstract universals of philosophy began to be supplanted, in the dominant intellectual discourse, by the ‘proven’ universals of science.

Western discourses of universalism developed in particular social and historical circumstances, as did their applications in and to the ‘real’ world, in contrast to their uses as abstractions of ideal and ideological worlds. The development of a comparable natural and modern ‘Buddhist universalism’ was inhibited by social and political circumstances. Buddhism and the East never enjoyed the opportunity which colonialism offered to the West – to impose its grid on the greater world from a position of absolute superiority and language dominance. Instead, in the colonial and the post-colonial periods, Buddhism had to squeeze itself into the second-hand frames of the predominant colonial thought-worlds, and to accept the systems of education and governance, the vocabulary, the ideologies, and the technologies, of European universalism. Even when Buddhism was dominant in terms of numbers or power equations, it remained ideologically subaltern. Buddhists raced to counter ‘superstition’, and to find compatibilities between Buddhism and science. This was so in East Asia, with the wholesale import of western concepts and intellectual tools from the eighteenth century on, and this was so in South and Southeast Asia, where education was designed and regulated by the colonial powers. In Indochina, for example, the *Instituts bouddhiques* in Cambodia and Laos were established by the French, not by the Buddhist *samghas*. Curricula followed European models, even in independent states like Siam.

Core Universals

Still, we can accept that universalism, like any other concept, may prove to be a useful analytic or conceptual tool for the study of Buddhism. Even so, it is a new tool, and it needs to be tested. Let us use it to open new insights, socially and philologically, in the study of Asian intellectual history. Can we find a universalism in Buddhism, in the Dharma of the Buddha, that goes back to the roots, to the most ancient periods, to the Master himself? I believe that a universalism can be found in specific social or human values, rather than in abstractions and dogmatics, which in the Buddhist value system are forms of *dr̥ṣṭi*, views or opinions. I will briefly examine the Buddhist notion of the universe and the terminological problems and choices posed by the very idea of the universal, and then discuss three themes: universal welfare, universal outreach, and universal message.

QUESTIONS OF TERMINOLOGY AND TRANSLATION

Welfare, benefit, is the foundation of Buddhist universalism. Concern for welfare is social and ecological – to love and to care for all sentient beings, without exception. This links to *maitrī* and the spiritual exercises of the *brahma-vihāras*, which are beyond the scope of this paper, except to note that the term is sometimes translated as ‘universal abidings’, taking ‘*brahma*’ as ‘universal’ – using a term loaded with ‘other’ meanings to express an Indian concept, as in the case of ‘universal *saṃgha*’. Concern for welfare leads naturally to universal outreach, a non-exclusive embrace of all beings. One of the pragmatic and moral results of this embrace is security: protection against all sorts of calamities and all sorts of malignant beings or spirits. The only protection is love, not opposition, denial, or exclusion. The universal message is love, and knowledge of the path that leads away from sorrow and suffering to well-being and happiness. The summa of insight is dependent arising, which entails the realization that all beings are interrelated.

The Open Universe

The English word ‘universal’ has its own meanings and its own pretensions: universal education, universal suffrage, universal rights, universal consciousness, universal language, Universal Studios. These usages express received social ideals, and the very use of the word ‘universal’ precludes any debate. Who could argue, even rhetorically, against universal suffrage, universal human rights, universal healthcare, or universal childcare?

But this study goes far back in time, to ancient India. Is there any Indic term for ‘universal’? In Buddhist usage, ‘universe’ can be *loka*, *lokadhātu*, *cakkavāḷa*, or even *buddhakṣetra*. *Loka* is global: the Buddha is *lokaguru*, ‘the world teacher’, ‘teacher of the world’.⁹ Other possibilities are *sādhāraṇa* or *samanta* or *sākala*. As a technical term in *Abhidharma* and *Pramāṇa*, *sādhāraṇa* is often translated as ‘universal’, but this sense is too limited for my purposes. *Samanta* (*saṃ* + *anta*), ‘all round’, may also be translated as ‘universal’, as in the name of the *bodhisatva* Samantabhadra, ‘Universally worthy’. But *samanta* does not go beyond the sense of entirety or comprehensiveness. *Sākala* (*sakon* สากล) as a loanword in Thai expresses the modern idea of universal. The word *viśva*, common in some universalist notions in Hindu thought and usage (Viśvarūpa Viṣṇu), is notably rare in Buddhism. This seems an interesting point, but I cannot follow it up here.

The Buddhist vision of the world is the field in which Buddhist thought develops:¹⁰

Just as the sun and moon by shining and moving illuminate the directions, so it is equally in a thousand worlds (*loka*), a thousand moons, a thousand suns, a thousand Sumerus which are the kings of mountains, a thousand four-continents, a thousand dwellings of the gods of the Assembly of the Four Great Kings, a thousand dwellings of the Thirty-Three gods, a thousand dwellings of the Yāmas, a thousand dwellings of the Joyous, a thousand dwellings of the Creative-Enjoyers, a thousand dwellings of the Controllers of Others' Creations, a thousand worlds of Brahma – this is called 'small chiliocosm' (*sahasracūḍiko lokadhātu*). A thousand 'small chiliocosms' are called 'second middling chiliocosm'. A thousand middling chiliocosms are called 'third megachiliocosm'. This 'trichilio-megachiliocosm' is girdled by a range of large circular mountains. The duration of the devolution and the evolution of this trichilio-megachiliocosm is the same.

Just as round drops of rain fall constantly and uninterruptedly from the sky, so equally in the Eastern direction, constantly and uninterruptedly, an infinite number of universes (*lokadhātu*) will devolve or evolve, devolve or remain devolved, or evolve or remain evolved. Just as it is in the Eastern direction, so it is in all the ten directions.

I cite here the north Indian philosopher Asaṅga, who lived in about the fourth century CE. But the basic cosmology is already fully developed in the early suttas and sūtras, where it is a ground, a prerequisite, for many of their ideas. If we wish to trace these concepts to the time of the Buddha himself, it is fifth century BCE. If we argue that the concepts belong to a wider, pan-Indian worldview, then they can go back further, much further. This is the background of Buddhist thought and of any idea of a 'Buddhist universal': a *longue durée* in a *longue étendue*. The universe is open and in constant flux. Universes come and universes go: they are beyond number. Buddhas too come and go: Buddhas are beyond number.

Terminological Choices: the Universal as 'sarvaṃ'

For me, the most relevant word in the quest for the universal in Buddhist usage is *sarvaṃ*, 'all': *sarva* in Sanskrit, *sabba* in Pāli, *sava* in Prakrit, *sarva* again in Gāndhārī. These terms are cognate with English 'whole'.¹¹ Often the word means total, totally, completely. A concern with completeness, with totality, is a characteristic of Buddhism, as of philosophers in general.

Sarva is used in inclusive statements in the *Nikāyas* and *Āgamas*:

All *dharmas* are impermanent ...
All *dharmas* are unsatisfactory ...
All *dharmas* are without self.¹²
Do not be attached to any *dharmas*.¹³

Sarva is used in the phrasing of their tenets by different streams of Buddhist thought:

Sarvam asti, Everything exists.
Citta-mātram idaṃ sarvaṃ, All this is only mind.¹⁴
Tathāgata-garbhāḥ sarve sattvāḥ, All beings are potential *tathāgatas*.¹⁵

Inclusive statements with ‘*sarva*’ are frequent in the Perfection of Wisdom literature, often in the form of dialectical negations: ‘all this is not empty, but it is not non-empty’ (*sarvam idaṃ na sūnyaṃ nāpi cāsūnyam*).

Here I will discuss *sarva* in connection with the world and sentient beings: *sarvaloka*, the ‘entire world’, the ‘whole world’, and *sarvasatva*, ‘all sentient beings’.

CONCERN FOR UNIVERSAL WELFARE AND HAPPINESS

Bhikkhus, there is one person who arises in the world for the welfare of many people, for the happiness of many people, out of compassion for the world, for the good, welfare, and happiness of devas and human beings. Who is that one person? The Tathāgata, the Arahant, the Perfectly Enlightened One. This is that one person who arises in the world for the welfare of many people, for the happiness of many people, out of compassion for the world, for the good, welfare, and happiness of devas and humans beings.¹⁶

Relics and Stūpas: the Beginnings of Buddhism

After the Buddha’s passing, his relics were divided and distributed, and *stūpas* were built to house them. Relics travelled royally across India on caparisoned elephants, and when they reached their destinations they were welcomed with music, song and dance. *Stūpas* were venerated by offering banners, parasols, flowers, and incense, by circumambulation and liturgical chants.

We do not have much evidence to understand the social history of Buddhism or early South Asia, and one of the best resources is the written word – the corpus of inscriptions engraved on stone and other durable

materials. The earliest written records are the edicts and proclamations of King Aśoka, who reigned from Pāṭāliputra (present-day Patna, Bihar State) in about the middle of the third century BCE. Aśoka had edicts and proclamations carved on natural stone and on stone pillars across his far-flung empire, which stretched from present-day Afghanistan in the west to Odisha on the Bay of Bengal in the east; from the southern plains of Nepal to Karnataka in the south of India. After Aśoka, the next corpus of inscriptions comes from early Buddhist monuments, especially the *stūpa* complexes and cave complexes. These date from the second century BCE, if not earlier, up to the second to third centuries CE – the focus of this essay – and later. The inscriptions are formulaic, but at the same time they reveal the public aspirations of donors from several parts of the subcontinent, and we can discern in them persistent themes. The early inscriptions of Aśoka and of the Buddhist donors and devotees are all in the Prakrits of the time. One of the most prominent themes is the well-being of the entire world or of all beings.

Aśoka's Concern for the World

Going back to the mid-third century BCE, we find that the compound *hita-sukha* (or *hida-sukha*) is frequent in the Aśokan inscriptions.¹⁹ These records reveal that the well-being and happiness of the whole world was one of the Emperor's chief concerns. In Pillar Edict 6, from the twenty-sixth year after his consecration, Aśoka states that he has had his Dhamma-inscriptions engraved 'for the well-being and happiness of the world' (*lokassā hita-sukhāye*), and he explains what he means by this.²⁰

In western India, in the modern state of Gujarat, is Girnar mountain (Dist. Junagadh), where Aśoka had edicts carved on a massive boulder. Below the 13th Girnar Rock Edict, on the right, is an inscription that reads, 'The all-white elephant bringing indeed happiness to the whole world'.²¹ The 'white elephant' is a term for the Buddha. On the opposite side of the subcontinent, at Dhauli and Jaugada in Kalinga (modern Odisha), Aśoka states in that 'all men are my children. As for my children I desire all well-being and happiness in this world and the world beyond, so do I wish for all men'.²² In Rock Edict 6,²³ Aśoka makes the following proclamation:

I consider my duty to be the well-being of the entire world;²⁴ the root of that is to work and to accomplish one's aims. There are no deeds superior to those for the well-being of the entire world. And all of the efforts I have made have been dedicated towards freeing myself from my debt to creatures. In this world I work for their happiness, and in the next world that they may reach

heaven. For this purpose, I have had this *Dhammalipi* engraved, that (this pronouncement) may endure for a long time, and that my sons, grandsons, and great-grandsons may follow suit by acting for the well-being of the entire world. But this is difficult without supreme effort.

Inscribed Reliquaries from Gandhāra

My first examples are from inscribed reliquaries from Gandhāra.²⁵ It is appropriate here to raise some questions: ‘Who are the authors of the inscriptions? Whose voice do we hear? Who is the intended audience?’ We do not know who composed the inscriptions – a monk or a ritual specialist, a trained scribe or stonemason, or a cooperation between the donor, his or her family, and those who produced the document. We can assume that the voice is that of the donor(s), and that the audience is at the minimum the donor’s circle of family and acquaintances, and probably the community associated with the *stūpa* or place of installation, including also the deities. Inscriptions show that people made merit for their own benefit, for their family members, for their ancestors, and for the rulers, the ‘state’. The short texts announce deeds of merit and invoke blessings – and also curses against those who damage or harm the relics.

Many reliquaries have no dedicatory inscriptions. In these cases, it is possible that the relics may have been dedicated orally in joint ceremonies at the site and were never formally recorded. In addition, there is evidence that dedications were written on birchbark or on perishable materials that have not survived.

The inscriptions state the purpose of the dedication and list the names of those who share in the merit. At the end the merit is directed to all beings, using a range of phrases. An early and simple dedication from Swat reads as follows:

By Theodotos, the meridarch, are established these relics of the Śākya sage, the Lord, for the benefit of many people (*bahujaṇahitāye*, § 3).²⁶

The inscription identifies the donor, his position, and the nature of the relics that he has had enshrined. His donation is for the benefit of the many people, *bahujaṇahitāya* – a phrase common in the early scriptures, including in the *eka-puggala* formula. Other dedications ‘honour’ all beings:

All beings are honoured (*sarvasatvapuyāita*, § 5).²⁷

All beings are honoured (*savasatvaṇa puyae*, § 14).²⁸

All who deserve honour are honoured (*ye sava puyaraha puyāida*, § 15).²⁹

All who deserve honour are honoured (*sarve pujaraha puyāita*, § 17).³⁰

All beings are honoured. All beings are brought to nirvana (*sarvasatva puyāita savasatva patinivāito*, § 25).

May it be for the honour (and) for the attainment of nirvana of all beings (*sarvasatvana puyae nivanasa pratīae hotu*, § 29).³¹

In honour of all beings. And this dependent arising has been written by Mahiphatia in honour of all beings (*sarvasatvana puyae aya ca praticasammupate likhida mahiphatiena sarvasatvana puyae*, § 39).³²

May it be for the benefit and happiness of all beings (*sarvasatvana hitasuhartha bhavatu*, § 45).³³

Numbers 25 and 29 wish or aim for all beings to attain nirvana. In Number 39, one of the participants has written out the full formula of dependent arising in ascending order. This is an early and dated example of a practice that became widespread, and one of the few in which the sponsor gives his name and intentions.

Inscriptions from Jaggayyapetta, Nagarjunakonda, and Kanaganahalli

Let us turn southward, to Jaggayyapetta and Nagarjunakonda in Tamil Nadu, and to Kanaganahalli in Karnataka.

Jaggayyapetta

Jaggayyapetta is an ancient *stūpa* site in the Krishna District of the former Madras Presidency, later Madras, now Tamil Nadu. Located about fifty km northwest of the celebrated Mahācaitya at Amaravati, it was discovered and excavated by James Burgess in February, 1882. Burgess found three ‘almost identical’ inscriptions, which close with the formula, ‘established for the welfare and happiness of all beings’ (*sava-satāna hitasukhāya patīḥāpita*).³⁴

Nagarjunakonda

At Nagarjunakonda, Āyaka-pillar inscription C 3 opens with:³⁵

Success! Homage to the Fortunate One, who is honoured by the kings of the gods, who has awakened to the well-awakened, who is omniscient, who is compassionate towards all sentient beings. He has conquered passion, hatred, and delusion, and he is thereby liberated. Leader of a great following, he is comparable to a bull or a musk-elephant. He is the truly and fully awakened one.³⁶

The donor is Mahātālavari Cāmtisiri, uterine sister of Mahārāja Vāsiṭhiputa Ikhāku Siri-Cāmtamūla. She has set up the pillar ‘to bring welfare and happiness in both worlds, for her own attainment of nirvāna, and to bring well-being and happiness for the entire world’.³⁷ Other royal donations at the site use the same or similar formulas. First Apsidal Temple Inscription E, for example, after giving the date, closes with:³⁸

May this be for the well-being and happiness of all beings (*sava-satānaṃ hitāya sukhāya hotu ti*).

Kanaganahalli

Kanaganahalli in Karnataka is a large stūpa that was excavated by the Archaeological Survey of India from the beginning of the 1990s and only recently published. The stūpa was encased with carved stone slabs bearing Prakrit inscriptions. At Kanaganahalli, the inscribed items are not reliquaries but the component parts of the stūpa. At Kanaganahalli – properly, the Adhāloka Mahācaitya according to an inscription – the idea of universal welfare was also prominent in the minds of the donors.

For the well-being and happiness of all beings (*sava-satāna ca hita-sughatha* § I.8).⁴⁰

For the well-being and happiness of the whole world (*sava-loka-hita-sughaya*, § I.10).⁴¹

For the well-being of the whole world (*sava-loka-sughaya*, § I.12).⁴²

For the well-being [of the whole world] (*sava-loka ...*, § I.14).⁴³

To venerate all Buddhas (*sava-budha-puyāya*, II.2.17).

For the well-being and happiness of the whole world (*sava-loka-hita-s[ughāya]*, § II.5.8).

To bring happiness to the world (§ II.6.1, *loka-sukhāvahāya*).⁴⁴

To bring well-being and happiness to all beings (§ II.6.2, *sava-satāna hita-sughāvahāya*).

For the well-being and happiness of the whole world (§ II.7.A.8, *sava-lokasa hita-sughā ca*).⁴⁵

At Kanaganahalli, eight seated Buddhas were placed at the four entrances or on the lower circumambulatory. All bear inscriptions on the bases.⁴⁶ These tell us that ‘this magnificent donation’ was sponsored by a lay follower named Visākha of the Vāgāḍhica family together with his sons. The set consists of the seven Buddhas of the past, including Śākyamuni, and Maitreya, the future Buddha. The Maitreya, with hands and head lost, was found in the southwestern part of the lower circumambulatory;⁴⁷ he is described on the pedestal as ‘the Fortunate One, the Bodhisatva Ajita, the future Buddha (*bhagavā bodhisato ayito anāgato budho*)’,

produced ‘for the well-being and happiness of the whole world’ (§ II.7.A.8, *sava-lokasa hita-sughā ca*). This must be the earliest image of Maitreya identified by an inscription, and one of the few that identifies the Bodhisatva Ajita with the future Buddha.

This ideal, ‘the benefit and happiness of all beings’, is also found in some inscriptions from Mathura.⁴⁸ In the cave monasteries of the Western Ghats, the aim is expressed at Karle⁴⁹ and at Nasik.⁵⁰ We find it in the Gangetic plain at Sarnath,⁵¹ and in Malwa at Sanchi.⁵² It is also expressed at Kaman (EHS 181) and in the Gundā and Gondal inscriptions (CE 181 and 350: EHS 201), which may or may not be Buddhist, and in several Jaina inscriptions. Damsteegt suggests that the use of the phrase ‘at least in some Mathurā Jaina inscriptions is due to relations with the North-West, although the possibility of an influence of the Mathurā Buddhists in some other cases cannot be excluded’ (EHS 170). Mathurā, as a Kuṣāṇa centre, was an interface between the Northwest and North India.⁵³ It is possible that the usage was associated with this or that Vinaya tradition, and was circulated by certain schools. Against this idea is the fact of the universal usage of the phrases in the known literature of the schools.

The Western Caves

Similar dedications are found in Western caves, for example at Kanheri.⁵⁴ They date from the second to early third centuries CE.

May this be for the well-being and happiness of all beings
(*savva-satānaṃ ca hita-sukhāya hotu*).⁵⁵

For the well-being and happiness of all beings (*sava-satānaṃ
hita-sughatha*).⁵⁶

May this be for the happiness of all beings (*sarvva-satvānaṃ ca
hita-sukhārthāya bhavatu*).⁵⁷

For the well-being of the whole world (*sava-lokasa hita-
sughatha*).⁵⁸

For the well-being and happiness of the whole world (*sava-
loka-hita-sukhāya ti*).⁵⁹

The Benefit of Books

One of the most remarkable advances in our knowledge of early Buddhism in recent years has been the publication of an ancient birchbark scroll containing two chapters of the Perfection of Wisdom (*Prajñāpāramitā*) written in the Gandhari Prakrit language in the Kharosthi script of the Northwest.⁶⁰ The colophon of the Gandhari manuscript, which dates to the first century CE, states:⁶¹

pathamage postage prañāparamidaē budha[mitra] ///
idraśavaśa sadhaviharisa imena ca kuśalamuleṇa
sarvasatvamatrapi(trap)u(?yae) ///

This is the first book of the *Prajñāpāramitā* (of) Buddhmitra (...), the disciple of Indraśava. May it be, through this root of goodness (...) for the veneration of all living beings, for mother and father.

This suggests that in the early period the motives for writing the Dharma down in manuscripts – for the beginnings of written culture – may have been similar to those that lay behind other ‘deeds of merit’, which would help strengthen the ‘roots of merit’, and were dedicated to relatives, here the parents, as well as to all sentient beings.

We also find the formula of altruism in a presumed Mahāyāna *sūtra* preserved in a birchbark scroll from Bajaur, Pakistan. The 84,000 gods who are receiving instruction from the Buddha announce to him:⁶²

We, Sir, O Fortunate One, aspire to unsurpassed, true and full awakening, for the sake of the non-interruption and the non-disappearance of the gift of the Dharma, for the well-being of many people, for the happiness of many people, out of compassion for the world, for the benefit, the well-being, and the happiness of gods and humans, for the non-interruption of the lineage of the Buddhas, for the well-being of all beings, for the happiness of all beings, out of compassion for the world, for the non-disappearance, growth, flourishing, non-confusion, and fulfillment of the Tathāgata’s teaching.

Here the sentiment of benefiting all beings is woven into the aspiration to awakening, through which an individual sets out to become a Buddha.

The concern for universal benefit starts with the earliest preserved Indian manuscripts of Mahāyāna texts – the Gandhari Perfection of Wisdom and the ‘Bajaur Mahāyāna Sūtra’ – and from then on continues to permeate Mahāyāna literature. In the opening of the *Lalitavistara*, the gods of the pure abodes request the Bodhisatva when he is still in the Tuṣita Heaven, to teach the *Lalitavistara*, which was taught by previous Tathāgata Samyaksambuddhas ‘for the well-being of many people, for the happiness of many people, out of compassion for the world, for the sake of the great mass of people, for the happiness of gods and men’.⁶³

In the opening of Mahāyāna *sūtras*, when an interlocuter asks the Buddha a question or series of questions, the Fortunate One responds

with a praise, using the ‘welfare module’. In the *Pratyutpannabuddha-sūtra*, for example, when Bodhisatva Bhadrupāla asks a question, the Fortunate One then says,⁶⁴

Well done, Bhadrupāla, well done! You, Bhadrupāla, have set out for the benefit of many beings, for the happiness of many beings, out of compassion for the world, for the welfare, the benefit, and the happiness of the great body of beings, of devas and of humankind, and you have done well, Bhadrupāla, in deciding to question the Tathāgata in such a way on this matter.

The Long Life of Simple Phrases

The simple phrases that express the wish for the benefit and happiness of all beings have had a long life, from the time of the Buddha to the present, for forms of it are still recited in rituals and prayers in Southeast Asia and Sri Lanka. It is remarkable that we can trace the aspiration from the Buddha to the inscriptions of Aśoka, and then epigraphically to Northwest India and throughout India. We can then follow it textually to living Theravāda Buddhism.

In sum, Buddhist universalism is seen in intention and motivation, in the thought-world of human activity. Buddhist action is mobilized not only for one’s own sake and the sake of one’s relations, but for the sake of all sentient beings. It is not for the sake of the Buddha (although supporting motives include, for example, to preserve the *Śāsana*). Deeds are not undertaken ‘for the glory of Buddha’, and ‘all sentient beings’ does not mean ‘all Buddhists’, or ‘all sentient beings who are connected in some way to Buddhism’. It means all sentient beings – humans, animals, deities, and spirits – universally and globally. This seems to be a remarkable and, perhaps, unique characteristic of Buddhism. It appears to me that in many religions, the approved motivation or inspiration is ‘for the glory of god’, and that this means the exclusive god of that religion alone, not the gods of others. While Buddhism is willing to embrace – ritually, metaphysically, and in narrative – all beings (*satva*, *bhūta*, *prāṇa*) – Brahmanism privileges the higher castes, while the Abrahamic religions restrict their scope to humans.

It is undeniable that, throughout a long and far-flung history, Buddhists and Buddhism have accommodated in various ways to the caste system and to unequal social structures. They have participated in and have perpetrated injustice. These are the brute facts of history. Ideal systems work, if at all, through compromise and interaction with existing realities.

Their records are never perfect, and the test of maturity is whether or not failures are recognized and whether attempts are made to redress injustice and to get back on the track to universal welfare. That Buddhists and Buddhism have often failed this test calls for rigorous and sincere self-assessment, but this topic is well beyond the scope of this essay.⁶⁵

If Buddhism has compromised socially, it has not done so philosophically. It has maintained its dissident position. Johannes Bronkhorst notes that, ‘Buddhists in India did not take long to accept the status quo when the Brahmanical layering of society managed to impose itself ... However, Buddhism never accepted the theoretical justification that saw in Brahmins a separate species. Indeed, the message preached by Buddhism concerned all human beings, irrespective of their social status; with respect to the Buddhist road to liberation, all human beings were equal. An ongoing debate about the equal or unequal status of human beings opposed Brahmanism and Buddhism for as long as they coexisted on the Indian subcontinent.’⁶⁶

Universal Outreach: Humanism and Cosmologism

Universal welfare is invoked in a verse that occurs in a variety of Indian Buddhist texts, and in inscriptions from Karnataka⁶⁷ and from Java:⁶⁸

sarve satvāḥ sarve prāṇāḥ sarve bhūtāś ca kevalāḥ |
sarve vai sukhiṇaḥ santu sarve santu nirāmayāḥ |
sarve bhadraṇi paśyantū mā kaścit pāpam āgamat ||

All beings, all breathing things, all creatures, inclusively,
 May all be happy, may all be of illness free
 May all see good things, may nobody encounter evil.

This leads us to ‘universal outreach’.

The Fortunate One, the ‘one person who arises in the world for the welfare of many people’, is the ‘teacher of gods and humans’, and he interacts at all levels with all of the beings defined or outlined in the cosmologies of the age. Two early texts that describe how this takes place are the *Mahāsamāja* and *Āṭānāṭīya Sūtras*. In the *Mahāsamāja-sūtra*, the gods and deities flock to listen to the Buddha’s teaching until they fill all space. In the *Āṭānāṭīya-sūtra*, the Great King Vaiśravaṇa imparts spells to protect monks and nuns, laymen and laywomen, against the malignant intentions of *yakṣas*, *gandharvas*, and other beings. These two long sūtras, included in the canons of the *Dīrghāgama/Dīghanikāya*, for the Mūlasarvāstivādins are ‘great sūtras’ (*mahāsūtras*) that bring

protection and blessing. To this day, the Pāli versions are recited in Theravādin ceremonies as powerful purifications and exorcisms. In the *Sagāthavagga* of *Samyuttanikāya*, the Buddha answers questions and overcomes challenges put by *yakṣas*, *devas*, and *māras*, etc.

In many Mahāyāna *sūtras*, the Buddha is waited upon by assemblies made up of all possible beings in the universe, who have come from multiple four-continent universes to see, to pay homage to, and to attend upon the Fortunate One, to listen to the Dharma: tens of thousands of *brahmās*, dozens of thousands of *śakras*, and other mighty and powerful *śakras*, *brahmās*, world guardians, *devas*, *nāgas*, *yakṣas*, *gandharvas*, *asuras*, *garuḍas*, *kinnaras*, and *mahoragas*. They take their places in the assembly with the monks and nuns, the laymen and laywomen, encircling the Fortunate One as he teaches the Dharma, rising up like Sumeru, King of Mountains from the middle of the ocean, seated on a lion throne, radiant, blazing, and shining.⁶⁹ At the end of the *sūtras*, ‘the whole assembly, and the world with its *devas*, humans, *asuras*, and *gandharvas* rejoices’.⁷⁰ In some *sūtras*, deities and mighty beings play the role of primary interlocutor: Druma the *kinnara* king, Sāgara the *nāga* king, Anavatapta the *nāga* king, and so on. It is their questions that inspire the discourse that follows. It is noteworthy that the Buddhist assemblies include beings who are excluded by orthodox brahmanism, such as the *Asuras*.⁷¹ All beings are welcome to listen to the Dharma, and all beings can gain salvation. All beings can set out on the path to awakening.

The beings who join to the assembly, the auditors and interlocutors, become devotees and followers of the Buddha, Dharma-practitioners and Dharma-protectors. The *Mahāmāyūrī*, an early protection text that went on to become one of the ‘Five Protections’ (*Pañcarakṣā*) of Northern India and Nepal, lists the names of *yakṣas* in relation to the cities of India. Sylvain Lévi called it a ‘geographical catalogue’.⁷² This work, an encyclopaedia of spirits, is one of the representative works of universalism.⁷³ These works are gender inclusive, in that the different beings and spirits are usually paired, male and female: *yakṣa* and *yakṣī*, *kinnara* and *kinnarī*, and so on. Females are welcome as donors, as listeners, and as protectors. In early art, donors appear as couples, often massive in size. At Bharhut, females are shown as guardians as well as worshippers. The five *Pañcarakṣā* texts are transformed into female deities, and female bodhisattvas like Tārā rise to great prominence.

The Golden Light *Sūtra* (*Suvarṇabhāsottama*) has chapters in which the Four Great Kings, Sarasvatī, Śrī, the Earth Goddess Ḍṛdhā, and the *Yakṣa* general Saṃjaya along with twenty-eight *yakṣa* generals successively promise protection. The Cloud *Sūtra* (*Megha-sūtra*) opens with the Buddha staying in the palace of the *nāga* kings Nanda and Upananda where he is attended by the great *nāga* kings and ‘84 hundreds of thousands of millions of crores’ of *nāgas*.⁷⁴ The assembly that gathers at Vulture’s Peak in Rājagṛha to listen to the Lotus *Sūtra* includes, in addition to monks, nuns, and bodhisattvas, a vast array of deities.⁷⁵ The opening of the *Laṅkāvatāra-sūtra* features Rāvaṇa, the demon (*rākṣasa*) king of Laṅkā, who invites the Buddha to his island. There he asks clarification of a celebrated dictum of the Buddha, ‘to relinquish *dharmas* – how much more so *adharmas*!’.⁷⁶ Rāvaṇa is the villain of the great epic, the *Rāmāyaṇa*. How is it that this *sūtra* is set in Laṅkādvīpa, how is it that Rāvaṇa is its ‘sponsor’?⁷⁷

It is these beings, the guardians, protectors, and supporters, who appear in early Buddhist art. They stand watch over *stūpa* complexes like Bharhut and Sanchi in the North, or Amaravati and Kanaganahalli in the South. Open to the sky, open to the elements, the *stūpas* were guarded by the four great celestial kings and by the spirits of the earth (*yakṣas*). We can see this in the text of the ‘Traikūṭaka copper plate’ found in a ruined caitya at Kanheri. After offering homage to the Omniscient One [the Buddha], the author requests the gods, *yakṣas*, *siddhas*, *vidyādharas*, *gaṇas*, Mañibhadra, Pūrṇabhadra, Pañcika, Ārya Vajrapāṇi, and Vāṅkana to look after the well-being of the *caitya*.⁷⁸ The early monuments were built through the collaboration of communities, of people of all stripes from nearby and from far and wide.⁷⁹ The *stūpa* complexes were the stages on which early Buddhism developed. Can we describe the *stūpa* as a universal monument?

In the realm of narrative, there are *jātakas* like the *Vidhura-jātaka* (No. 545) which opens with a chess-game played by a Śakra, a Nāga king, a Suparṇa king, and Dhanañjaya, the (human) king of Kuru; the plot that unfolds is a macabre romance between a *yakṣa* and a *nāga* princess. The *Sudhana-avadāna* is a long love affair between a human prince and a *kinnarī* maiden, a widely popular story that travelled from India to Java to Siam and Tibet. These were some of the most popular and enduring tales of Buddhism. Is it then narrative, a fictional universalism, that is the stage for playing out human emotions and transcendence? In the narratives of Mahāyāna universalism, events unfold at lightning speed

across galactic distances and mind-boggling time periods, played out by a pantheon of beings from the animal and spirit worlds to the highest heavens. The implied audience stretches the limits of the mythological imagination, but, let us remember, the Fortunate One is ‘teacher of gods and men’.

What is the purpose of this universal outreach? It shows that the Buddha is *devātideva*, god beyond the gods. The gods need his teachings and seek them out. In many cases, for example in the *Āṭānāṭṭiya-sūtra* or the *Mahāmāyūrī-vidyārājñī*, the text enlists the protection of the whole panoply of beings, transforming them from threats to allies and protectors. The deities protect the Buddha. They protect the *sūtras* and those who preach them. Vajrapāṇi is not only Śākyamuni’s bodyguard: he is bodyguard of each of the thousand Buddhas of the Auspicious Aeon. And the deities possess magical spells which they transmit to the Buddhas (many of the deities take on special roles in the Tantra, and their retinues are inducted into the *maṇḍalas*). The Buddha’s relationship to the gods and powerful beings highlights his status as a superman, a Great Man or *mahāpuruṣa*. The Buddha’s auditors include, and even welcome, people who are beyond the pale of brahmanical social interaction. The Buddha uses whatever language is appropriate to the listeners, even the language of the *mlecchās*.⁸⁰ He transmits *dhāraṇīs* in Dravidian languages (*drāmiḍa-vidyā*). In the brahmanical tradition, Āryās were prohibited from learning *mlecchā* languages (which can include Damila), and from any social interaction with them.⁸¹

Further, let us recall that the *varṇa* system prevailed in India. How and in what way, and the degree to which caste was class, was flexible, or was in continual flux, remains a subject of debate. But let us settle for this: the ideological system, the teaching of the Vedas, was in the hands of the brahmans, as were the Vedic rituals. That is to say, one caste controlled ‘religion’ as its birthright. The brahmanical system, which at the time of the Buddha was expanding its range of influence, was anything but universal in terms of accessibility and social outreach.⁸² The Buddhists and the other *Śramaṇas*, like the Jains, contended against a discriminatory and non-universalist system. The Buddhists reached out to all beings, and this was exemplified in the Mahāyāna *sūtras*.

‘*Buddhist Humanism*’, ‘*Buddhist Rationalism*’

The ideas outlined so far may not, however, fit well with the ‘Buddhist humanism’ and ‘Buddhist rationalism’ that developed with the Victorian

reception of Buddhism, but that is yet another question. There are many Buddhas, and among them, the ‘rational Buddha’ is powerful in the present age. The Buddhas of living Buddhism might seem unacceptable to some who had deep respect for the rational Buddha. Nehru, for example, wrote that,⁸³

When I visited countries where Buddhism is still a living and dominant faith, I went to see the temples and the monasteries and met monks and laymen ... There was much I did not like. The rational ethical doctrine had become overlaid with so much verbiage, so much ceremonial, canon law, so much, in spite of the Buddha, metaphysical doctrine and even magic. Despite Buddha’s warning, they had deified him, and his huge images, in the temples and elsewhere, looked down upon me and I wondered what he would have thought.

If the universal ‘deified Buddha’ is brought down from his pedestal, it is only to be replaced by the ‘historical Buddha’ with his rational, and hence universal teaching.⁸⁴

The Buddha’s Universal Message

One appeal of the Buddha’s teaching is that it is presented as a universal insight, rather than as an intellectual system. His insights might be formulated as the four truths of the noble ones, or as dependent arising. Both have been presented as the heart of his teaching.

At Śrāvastī, a monk went to the Fortunate One, and asked him:⁸⁵

‘Was dependent arising created by the Fortunate One, or was it created by others?’

The Buddha replied: ‘I did not create dependent arising. Nor did anyone else. Whether Tathāgatas arise, or whether Tathāgatas do not arise, this nature of things remains, the element which is the ground of *dharmas*. This the Tathāgata realizes by himself, and when he has realized it, he proclaims it, explains it, and reveals it.

The Buddha gives a succinct account of his attainment and teaching in the Sūtra on the Simile of the City. He describes his realization of dependent arising in detail, and then he goes on to say:⁸⁶

Just as a man wandering in the wilderness, on the mountainous slopes, might come across an ancient road, an ancient route, an ancient highway once travelled by the men of times past. He might follow it, and he might see an ancient city, an ancient royal capital, endowed with pleasure groves, woods, and lotus

ponds, beautiful, glorious,⁸⁷ and delightful. He would inform the king, who would rebuild the city, and in time this royal capital would be mighty, prosperous, and secure, with plenty to eat, bustling with crowds of people.

Just so, monks, I have found an ancient road, an ancient route, an ancient highway once travelled by the sages of times past. What is this ancient path? It is the noble eightfold path. I followed it, and I saw ageing and death; I saw the origin, the cessation, and the practice that leads to the cessation of ageing and death. I understood the whole of dependent arising, and when I had realized these realities by and for myself, I taught them to monks, nuns, laymen, and laywomen, to other *tīrthyas*, *śramaṇas* and brahmins, to *Carakas* and *Parivrājakas*. When a monk sets out, practising correctly, he realizes the method, the Dharma, the good. When a nun, a layman, or a laywoman sets out, practising correctly, she or he realizes the method, the Dharma, the good. In this way, the holy life has become widespread, has flourished among numerous people, and has been correctly proclaimed by gods and humans.

The truths stand, they endure, they are truths for all beings. The teaching is nothing beyond the end of suffering:⁸⁸

O monks, dependent states are suffering. The arising of suffering is from the arising of its causes; the cessation of suffering is from the cessation of its causes. Severed, the path cannot continue. Without any further connecting, it ceases. Just this is the end of suffering.

Phenomena, entities, dharmas, do not stand up to scrutiny: insight into dependent arising leads to the realization of emptiness. This a middle way is beyond extremes and polar or dualistic ideas, and it leads beyond conflict.⁸⁹ Dependent arising has its own universals; these are explained through conventional designation, without attachment.⁹⁰

Because there is no such thing as a dharma that is not dependently arisen, therefore there is no such thing as a dharma which is not empty.

In principle, anyone can access the truths, if they have the perseverance to practice. Nothing can stand outside Dharmatā, the laws of nature and the moral order. The moral practices of Buddhism are universal, an ideal for all humankind. Dharma is transcendental, transhistorical; it has been taught by an endless succession of Buddhas in endless universes throughout endless space. Dharma is a universal good, true and beautiful.

The Rise of Universalism

Buddhist universalism is expressed in literature – in the increasingly sophisticated metaphysics of the Abhidharma schools, which sought to explain *everything*, at all times and on all planes, and in the literary and philosophical gymnastics of the Mahāyāna. The drive to universalism seems to have been connected with the concept of ‘omniscience’, *sarvajñatā*, which rose to the fore after the Buddha’s passing (and probably not long after).⁹¹ The Teacher became all-knowing, and ‘all-knowledge’ took the place of ‘awakening’ as the goal for bodhisatvas. Omniscience is indeed one facet of the turn to universalism.

Universalism deeply affected Buddhist attitudes towards the use of language and languages, and the culture of translation that flourished both in India and abroad was impelled by the ideal of universal communication. The Buddha developed a balanced and practical theory of language use. He emphasized the conventional nature of language; he recommended that one follow conventional usages without attachment, most famously in the *Araṇavibhaṅga-sutta* (*Majjhima-nikāya* 139). The idea developed that the Buddha spoke in all languages, or that he could be understood by members of the audience, each in his or her own language. There was no Sanskrit cosmopolis, only communities of shared knowledge and shared languages. Recent manuscript studies, especially of the Buddhist literature of Gandhāra, make it increasingly clear that Buddhists fostered an ideology of writing long before other Indian religions. Works like the *Karmavibhaṅga* (which is best described as a ‘shared’ (*sādhāraṇa*) text), Mahāyāna *sūtras* like the *Akṣayamatīrdeśa* and the *Bodhisatvapiṭaka*, and Nāgārjuna’s verse *Ratnāvalī* all laud the benefits of offering manuscripts, ink, and pens.⁹² Universalism – universal benefit and universal communication – were among the forces that inspired Buddhist manuscript culture, and ultimately, perhaps, print technology. All of this continued to be done for the welfare and benefit or the world, for the good and the happiness of all sentient beings.

Keywords

- *hita, attha (artha), sukha* : benefit, well-being, happiness
- *anukampā* : compassion
- *loka, jagat, satta, bahujana* : world, people, beings, multitudes
- *lokadhātu, cakkavāḷa, buddhakṣetra* : world, universe
- *sabba (sarva)* : all, entire, whole

Notes

1. I originally presented this paper at the symposium 'L'universalisme bouddhique dans l'histoire des civilisations asiatiques' held at Kyoto University, 3–5 October, 2014. I am grateful to the participants in the conference for their comments and suggestions, in particular to Yuko Yokochi and Diwakar Acharya for their remarks as respondents.
2. Note that the term *cāturdiśa-saṃgha* (Pāli *cātuddisa-saṃgha*), 'saṃgha of the four quarters' or 'four directions', which is frequent in texts and in inscriptions, with reference to members of the *saṃgha* without restriction as a local or particular *saṃgha*, is frequently translated into English as 'universal *saṃgha*', and is perhaps a good example of the encroachment of 'universalist thought' into Buddhist terminology.
3. 'Religions universelles et religions particulières', Tokyo: Shūkyogaku, 1928; reprinted in *Mémorial Sylvain Lévi*, [Paris, 1937], repr. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1996, 126–132; citation from last named, 'Retrospective: L'Oeuvre complet de Sylvain Lévi', Item 289, p.472.
4. 'A Review of the Universal Exhibitions from 1851 to 1900': Musée d'Orsay, <http://www.musee-orsay.fr/en/collections/universal-exhibitions.html>, seen 15 October 2014.
5. Oskar von Hinüber, 'Origins and Varieties of Buddhist Sanskrit', in *Dialectes dans les littératures Indo-Aryennes*, ed. Colette Caillat, Paris: Collège de France, Institut de Civilisation Indienne, 1989, 361 (full article, 341–367). The reference is to Hara Prasad Shāstri, *Buddhist Manuscripts*: Vol. 1 of *A Descriptive Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts in the Government Collection under the Care of the Asiatic Society of Bengal*, Calcutta: Baptist Mission Press, 1917, 77.
6. Unless otherwise stated, translations are my own. *Sūtra* citations are usually somewhat abbreviated.
7. *he katholike ekklesia*, from the Greek καθολικός [*katholikos*] meaning 'universal', first used to describe the Church in the early second century CE.
8. Contemporary imaginings that the Enlightenment meant scientific and secular thought are in general wide off the mark. The degree to which one intellectual trend, Orientalism, was embedded in Christian monotheism and obfuscated by the preconceptions and inaccurate and incomplete information of the age is made clear in Urs App, *The Birth of Orientalism*, Philadelphia and Oxford: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2010.
9. Ajanta, Cave XVI, verandah: Inscription No. 3 in Jas. Burgess and Pandit Bhagwanlal Indraji, *Inscriptions from the Cave-Temples of Western India with Descriptive Notes, &c.*, [1881] Delhi: Indian India, 1976, 70, l. 17 (tr. 72); Vasudev Vishnu Mirashi, *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. V, *Inscriptions of the Vākātakas*, No. 25 (Pl. XXV), 'Ajañṭā Cave Inscription of Varāhadeva', 103–111; Tsukamoto III Ajañṭā 52.17. Reedited by Richard S. Cohen in Walter M. Spink, *Ajanta: History and Development*, Vol. 2, *Arguments about Ajanta*, Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2006, Inscription 67, 311–313.
10. *Abhidharmasamuccaya: The Compendium of the Higher Teaching (Philosophy) by Asaṅga, Originally translated into French and annotated by Walpola Rahula; English version from the French by Sarah Boin-Webb*, Fremont, California: Asian Humanities Press, 2001, pp 82–83 (French by Rahula, 60–61; Sanskrit ed. Pradhan, 36–37).
11. And compare Avestan *haurva*, Gr. *holos*, Lat. *solidus* and *soldus*, perhaps also *salvus*): see *The Pali Text Society's Pāli-English Dictionary*, [1921–1925] London, 1972, 680.
12. *Dhammapada*, verses 277–279.
13. *Sabbe dhammā nālaṃ abhinivesāya*, MN 37 (*Cūḷatañhāsaṅkhaya-sutta*), I 251.21, 254–5; SN IV 50; AN IV 88.
14. Bunyiu Nanjio (ed.), *The Lañkāvatāra Sūtra*, Kyoto: Otani University Press, 1923 (Bibliotheca Otaniensis, Vol. 1), Sagāthakam, v. 625.
15. Kamalaśīla, *Madhyamakāloka*, restored text: *Madhyamakāloka of Ācārya Kamalaśīla*, restored and critically edited by Dr. Penpa Dorjee, Sarnath, Varanasi: Central Institute of Higher Tibetan Studies (Bibliotheca Indo-Tibetica Series LXVV), 2001, 20.4.
16. *Aṅguttaranikāya* I 22.3, *ekapuggalo bhikkhave loke uppajjamāno uppajjati bahujaṇahitāya bahujaṇasukhāya lokānukampāya atthāya hitāya sukhāya devamanussānaṃ. katamo ekapuggalo? tathāgato araham sammāsambuddho. ayaṃ kho bhikkhave ekapuggalo loke*

uppajjamāno uppajjati bahujanahitāya bahujanasukhāya lokānukampāya atthāya hitāya sukhāya devamanussānam.

Translation by Bhikkhu Bodhi (tr.), *The Numerical Discourses of the Buddha: A Translation of the Aṅguttara Nikāya*; Somerville MA: Wisdom Publications, 2012, 107–108. There is a parallel in *Ekottarikāgama* (T. 125, 卷 *juān* 3, 561a9 – ref. from Lamotte, as per following), and the passage is incorporated into Mahāyāna sūtras like the *Śūraṅgama-samādhi* (tr. Étienne Lamotte, *La Concentration de la Marche Héroïque (Śūraṅgamasamādhisūtra)*, Brussels, 1975, § 71, 186 (Tibetan text given in footnote 162) and the *Akṣayamatī-nirdeśa*, (*Blo gros mi zad pas bstan pa*, Otani Cat. No. 842, Repr. vol. 34. *mdo, bu*, 156b2 = Jens Braarvig, *Akṣayamatīnirdeśa*, Vol. I, *Edition of extant manuscripts with an index*, Oslo: Solum Forlag, 1993, 118.29; idem, Vol. II, *The Tradition of Imperishability in Buddhist Thought*, 452–453.) The use of ‘person’ (*puggala*) in the passage is brought up in debates on the existence or non-existence of the person at *Kathāvattu* (PTS ed.) 65.18–20; in the chapter on the Puggala of the *Abhidharmakośabhāṣya: ekaḥ pudgalaḥ loka utpadyamāna utpadyate iti vacanāt*, P. Pradhan (ed.), *Abhidharma Kośabhāṣya of Vasubandhu*, Patna: K.P. Jayaswal Research Institute, 1967, 468.14 (Louis de La Vallée Poussin, L’*Abhidharmakośa de Vasubandhu*, Tome V, 259, in the mouth of a Vatsīputrīya); cited in Kumārajīva’s *Da zhidu lun*: Étienne Lamotte (tr.), *Le Traité de la Grande Vertu de Sagesse de Nāgārjuna (Mahāprajñāpāramitāśāstra)*, Tome I, Louvain: Institut Orientaliste, 1949 (Réimpr. 1966) 29, 73.

17. I refer in this essay to one of the most useful tools: TSUKAMOTO Keisho, *A Comprehensive Study of the Indian Buddhist Inscriptions, Part I, Text, Notes, and Japanese Translation*, Kyoto: Heirakuji-Shoten, 1996; idem, Part II, *Indices, Maps and illustrations*, Kyoto: Heirakuji-Shoten, 1998; idem, Part III, *Inscriptions in Northern areas, Pakistan*, Kyoto: Heirakuji-Shoten, 2003.
18. With the exception of several Aśokan inscriptions in the Northwest, written in Aramaic and Greek.
19. For the sites and bibliography, I refer to Harry Falk, *Aśokan Sites and Artefacts, A Sourcebook with Bibliography*, Mainz am Rhein: Verlag Philipp von Zabern, 2006.
20. Jules Bloch, *Les inscriptions d’Asoka*, Paris: Société d’Édition ‘Les Belles Lettres’, 1950 (Collection Émile Senart), 167.11.
21. (*sa*)*rva-sveto hasti sarva-loka-sukhāharo nāma*: E. Hultsch, *Inscriptions of Aśoka*. New edition. *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. I, repr. Delhi 1969, 26–27; Falk, *Aśokan Sites*, 118–120.
22. Separate Edict 1: Bloch, *Les inscriptions d’Asoka*, 137.3/4, Jaugada, *save munissā me pajā aṭha pajāye icchāmi kimti me savvena hitasukhena yujjeyū ti hidalogikapālalokikena hemeva me iccha savvamunissesu*. Cp. Edict II, Bloch 141.4/5. See Falk, *Aśokan Sites*, 113–115 (Dhauri); 121–123 (Jaugada).
23. Bloch, *Les inscriptions d’Asoka*, 108–110.
24. ‘World’, *loka*, also mean ‘people’, as it still does in Hindustani. We must investigate what it denoted in Aśoka’s vocabulary and time.
25. I cite the inscriptions from David Jongeward, Elizabeth Errington, Richard Salomon, and Stefan Baums (eds.), *Gandharan Buddhist Reliquaries*, Seattle: University of Washington Press/Early Buddhist Manuscripts Project, 2012, Chap. 6 by Stefan Baums, ‘Catalog and Revised Texts and Translations of Gandharan Reliquary Inscriptions’, reference by catalogue number as “§”.
26. ‘Paleographically not later than the middle of the first century BCE’ – n. 6, p. 204.
27. Early decades of first century BCE – see n.13, p. 205.
28. Relic-chamber slab dated 16/17 CE.
29. Dating to about 16/17 CE – see § 14.
30. Dated 19/20 CE.
31. Dated 76/77 CE.
32. The ‘Kurram casket’, a copper miniature *stūpa*, 146/147 CE.
33. Second half of second century CE – n. 97, p. 246.
34. G. Bühler, ‘Inscriptions from the Stupa of Jaggayyapettā’, *The Indian Antiquary*, edited

- by Jas. Burgess, Vol. XI, September 1882 (repr. Delhi: Swati Publications, 1984), 256–259; James Burgess, *The Buddhist Stupas of Amaravati and Jaggayyapeta in the Krishna District, Madras Presidency, surveyed in 1882, with Translations of the Aśoka inscriptions at Jaugada and Dhaulī by Georg Bühler*, [1886], Repr. Archaeological Survey of India, 1996 (Archaeological Survey of Southern India, Vol. VI), 110–111. See Tsukamoto, II (Jaggayyapeta 1–3), 305–307.
35. J. Ph. Vogel, ‘Prakrit Inscriptions from a Buddhist Site at Nagarjunikonda’, *Epigraphia Indica* XX, 1–36, Āyaka-pillar inscription C 3, 15–17. The text exists in nine redactions; Vogel gives only C 3, noting some of the variant readings in the others.
 36. *śiḍhaṃ namo bhāgavato devarāja-sakatasa supabudha-bodhino sava-sat-ānukampakasa jita-rāga-dosa-moha-vipamutasa mahāgaṇi-vasabha-gaṇḍha-hathisa saṃma-sambudhasa.*
 37. *chātisiri (apano ubhaya-kulasa atichitam-anāgata-vaṭamānākānaṃ parināmetunaṃ) ubhaya-loka-hita-sukhāvahathanāya atano ca nivaṇa-saṃpati-saṃpādake sava-loka-hita-sukhāvathanāya ca imaṃ khaṃbhaṃ patīthapitaṃ.*
 38. Vogel, *Epigraphia Indica* XX, p. 21.
 39. The official report is K.P. Poonacha, *Excavations at Kanaganahalli (Sannati), Taluk Chitapur; Dist. Gulbarga, Karnataka*, New Delhi: Archaeological Survey of India, 2011 (Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India No. 106, released 2013). Regrettably, the treatment of the epigraphic material is inadequate; all references to inscriptions are to Oskar von Hinüber, *Annual Report of the International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhism at Soka University for the Academic Year 2013*, Vol. XVII, Tokyo: The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhism, Soka University, 2014; Supplement: *Kanaganahalli Inscriptions*, by text number.
 40. Dated CE 120.
 41. Dated CE 125/131.
 42. Dated CE 181.
 43. Dated CE 225–230.
 44. The phrase, on the pedestal of a Buddhapāda, is fragmentary and conjectural. See following.
 45. On the pedestal of a seated Buddha, who, according to the inscription, is the Fortunate One, the Bodhisatva Ajita, the future Buddha (*bhagavā bodhisato ayito anāgato budho*).
 46. See von Hinüber, § II.7, A, 76–81. For pictures of the Buddhas, see Poonacha, Pls. CXXVII, CXXVIII.
 47. See Poonacha, *Excavations at Kanaganahalli*, Pl. CXXVII D.
 48. References in this paragraph are to EHS = Th. Damsteegt, *Epigraphical Hybrid Sanskrit: Its rise, spread, characteristics and relationship to Buddhist Hybrid Sanskrit*, Leiden: E.J. Brill, 1978 (Orientalia Rheno-Traiectina XXIII). For Mathura, see *sarvasatvānaṃ hitasukhāye* or *-sukhārthaṃ*, with some variants: EHS 160 [late Kṣatrapa], 167, 168 [nāga].
 49. *sava-satānaṃ hita-sugha-sthataye*, EHS 177–178.
 50. VII, *sarva-satva-hita-sukhārthaṃ*, EHS 180.
 51. I, *sarva-satvanaṃ hita-su. khārthaṃ*, EHS 179.
 52. EHS 183–184. The phrase is not, apparently, found at Bharhut or, in the early period, at Sanchi, where it is absent in the reliquary inscriptions of the Hemavata teachers retrieved from the ‘Bhilsa topes’. These seem all to be simple labels identifying the relics.
 53. One phrase that is common in the Northwest also occurs at Mathura (*sarvabudhapujāye*, EHS 159–160), Kosam (II, *savabudhānaṃ pujāye*, EHS, 174), and Nasik (V, *savabudhapujāya*, EHS 175).
 54. I cite here Shobhana Gokhale, *Kanheri Inscriptions*, Pune: Deccan College Post Graduate and Research Institute, 1991.
 55. Gokhale, *Kanheri Inscriptions*, p. 51 ll. 14–15. Where the editor reads *hetu*, I correct to *hotu*: the photograph is difficult to make out, but an “o” above the “ta” can be fairly discerned (line 4 of the right-hand photo on p. 50).
 56. Gokhale, *Kanheri Inscriptions*, No. 25, pp. 75–76.

57. Gokhale, *Kanheri Inscriptions*, No. 33, pp. 86–88.
58. Gokhale, *Kanheri Inscriptions*, No. 34, p. 88.
59. Gokhale, *Kanheri Inscriptions*, No. 35, p. 88.
60. See Peter Skilling, 'Prakrit Prajñāpāramitā: Northwest, South, and Center: Gleanings from Avalokitavratā and Haribhadra', *Bulletin of the Asia Institute New Series/Volume 23* (2009) (Carol Altman Bromberg, Timothy J. Lenz, and Jason Neelis, ed., *Evo suyādi: Essays in Honor of Richard Salomon's 65th Birthday*), 199–208; see also Peter Skilling, 'Vaidalya, Mahāyāna, and Bodhisatva in India: An essay towards historical understanding,' in Bhikkhu Nyanatusita (ed.), *The Bodhisatva Ideal: Essays on the Emergence of the Mahāyāna*. Kandy: Buddhist Publication Society, 69–162 (especially 72–74).
61. Harry Falk and Seishi Karashima, 'A first-century *Prajñāpāramitā* manuscript from Gandhāra – *parivarta 1*', *ARIRIAB XV* (2012), 19–61 with pls. 5–7 (Texts from the Split Collection 1), p. 25 and fig. 3.
62. Ingo Strauch, 'More Missing Pieces of Early Pure Land Buddhism: New Evidence for Akṣobhya and Abhirati in an Early Mahayana Sutra from Gandhāra', *The Eastern Buddhist* 41 (2010), 28–29 (full article pp. 23–66), [7.9] *caduraśidī ca devasaḥaṣa vāya bhaṣati vae bhate bhagava · eḍa[sa dha]ma[sa daṇaṣa] aṣamochedae anātarahaṇae ca · bahajanahidāe bahajā[na]-[7.10] (*suha)e loa[nuapae arthae hidae suhae devamanuṣāna budhanetria[nuchedae sarvasatvahidāe sarvasatvasuhae loa[nuapae tasagadaśaśa-[7.11] (*nasa) anata[ra]haṇae · ...*
63. Hokazono Kōichi, *Raritavisutara no Kenkyū* (Jyō-kan [Vol. 1]), Tokyo: Daitō Shuppansha, 1995, 276–277, *bahujanahitāya bahujanasukhāya lokānukampāya mahato janakāyasyārthāya sukhāya devānām ca manuṣyānām*. The relation of the *Lalitavistara* to the 'Mahāyāna' is not clear-cut, but its current recension it is held to belong to the Mahāyāna by the Nepalese and Tibetan traditions. Much of its contents are certainly shared or *sādhāraṇa*.
64. Translation after Paul Harrison (tr.), *The Samādhi of Direct Encounter with the Buddhas of the Present: An Annotated English Translation of the Tibetan Version of the Pratyutpanna-Buddha-Sammukhāvasthita-Samādhi-Sūtra with Several Appendices relating to the History of the Text*, Tokyo: The International Institute for Buddhist Studies, 1990 (Studia Philologica Buddhica Monograph Series V), [2A]. For the Tibetan Text, see idem, *The Tibetan Text of the Pratyutpanna-Buddha-Sammukhāvasthita-Samādhi-Sūtra, Critically edited from the Derge, Narthang, Peking, and Lhasa Editions of the Tibetan Kanjur and accompanied by a Concordance and Comparative Table of Chapters of the Tibetan and Chinese Versions*, Tokyo: The Reiyukai Library, 1978 (Studia Philologica Buddhica Monograph Series I), [2]. Cp. *Sūraṅgamasamādhisūtra, The Concentration of Heroic Progress, An early Mahāyāna Buddhist Scripture* translated and annotated by Étienne Lamotte, English translation by Sara Boin-Webb, Richmond, Surrey & London: Curzon Press in association with the Buddhist Society, 1998, § 8, spoken by the Buddha to bodhisatva Dṛḍhamati.
65. On this subject see Peter Skilling, 'Buddhism: Imperfection and Transcendence,' *Journal for the Comparative Study of Civilizations (Reitaku University)* 11: 26–32 [International Symposium to Commemorate the 10th Anniversary of the Center for the Comparative Study of Civilizations and Cultures].
66. Johannes Bronkhorst, *Karma*, Honolulu, University of Hawai'i Press, 2011, pp. 50–51.
67. Tsukamoto I (III) Dambal 2, p. 394; J.F. Fleet, 'Sanskrit and Old-Canarese Inscriptions', *Indian Antiquary* X, 187 (full article, 185–190). See Peter Skilling, *Mahāsūtras: Great Discourses of the Buddha*, Vol. II, Parts I & II, Oxford: The Pali Text Society, 1997 (Sacred Books of the Buddhists XLVI), 595–596.
68. There is, however, more to it than that: I have been unable to trace the verse to any Brahmanical text, but it is widely known and widely recited by modern Hindus. There are many variant versions: for this version, see *Mahāmantrānusāriṇī* in Peter Skilling, *Mahāsūtras: Great Discourses of the Buddha*, Vol. I. *Texts: Critical editions of the Tibetan Mahāsūtras with Pāli and Sanskrit counterparts as available*, Oxford: The Pali Text Society, 1994 (Sacred Books of the Buddhists XLIV), C.3.14–16, pp. 614–615. In Java, the verse is on gold plates of the *Sūtra* of dependent arising with a commentary thereon.

69. *Vimalakīrtinirdeśa* = Study Group on Buddhist Sanskrit Literature (ed.), *Bonzōkan Taisho Yuimagyō 梵藏漢对照『維摩經』 Vimalakīrtinirdeśa: Transliterated Sanskrit Text Collated with Tibetan and Chinese Translations*, The Institute for Comprehensive Studies of Buddhism, Tokyo: Taisho University, 2004, §§ 5, 6 (abbreviated translation).
70. *Vimalakīrtinirdeśa* § 23, p. 125, *sā ca sarvāvātī parṣat sadevamānuṣūsuragandharvaś ca loka bhāgavato bhāṣitam abhyanandann iti*.
71. For a discussion of *Asuras* in Mahāyāna *sūtras* vis à vis in the Brahmanical *Dharmaśāstras*, see Madhav M. Deshpande, ‘What to do with the Anāryas? Dharmic discourses of inclusion and exclusion’, in Johannes Bronkhorst and M. Deshpande (ed.), *Aryan and Non-Aryan in South Asia: Evidence, Interpretation and Ideology*, repr. New Delhi: Manohar, 2012 (first published in *Opera Minora* by Harvard Oriental Series, Cambridge, Mass., 1999), 121–124 (full article, 107–127).
72. English version by Prabodh Chandra Bagchi, ‘The Geographical Catalogue of the Yakṣas in the Mahāmāyūrī’, [*Sino-Indian Studies*, Vol. III Parts I & II, pp. 13–87] Repr. in *Indological Studies: A Collection of Essays*, Santiniketan: Visva-Bharati, 1982, 420–500.
73. For a translation see J.F. Marc des Jardins, *Le sūtra de la Mahāmāyūrī: rituel et politique dans la Chine des Tang (618–907)*, Presses de l’Université Laval, 2011.
74. Cecil Bendall, ‘The Megha-Sūtra’, *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland*, New Series, Vol. 12, No. 2 (April 1880), 288/289 (full article, 286–311).
75. Jean-Noël Robert (tr.), *Le Sūtra du Lotus, suivi du Livre des sens innombrables et du Livre de la contemplation de Sage-Universal*, Paris: Librairie Arthème Fayard, 1997, 46–49.
76. Bunyiu Nanjio (ed.), *The Lañkāvatāra Sūtra*, Kyoto: Otani University Press, 1923 (*Bibliotheca Otaniensis*, Vol. 1), 17.2.
77. We note that the demon king soon drops out of the narrative, and Bodhisatva Mahāmātī becomes the interlocutor from Chap. 2 on. The king attains an advanced stage of insight, described at 9.11 foll., and realizes, or is on the verge of realizing, *anuṣṭipattikadharmakṣāntī* (12.9).
78. Gokhale, *Kanheri Inscriptions*, No. 14, 59–61.
79. We can see this in the sections on the distribution of relics in the *Mahāparinirvānasūtras* and in the early donative inscriptions.
80. See Jin-il Chung and Klaus Wille, ‘Fragment aus dem Bhaiṣajyavastu der Sarvāstivādins in der Sammlung Pelliot (Paris)’, *Sanskrit-Texte aus dem buddhistischen Kanon: Neuentdeckungen und Neueditionen IV* (Sanskrit-Wörterbuch der buddhistischen Texte aus den Turfan-Funden, Beiheft 9), Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2002, 121–122 (full article, 105–125; *Jñānaprasthāna* cited in J. Takakusu, ‘On the Abhidharma Literature of the Sarvāstivādins’, *Journal of the Pālī Text Society* 1904–1905, 98 (full article, 65–146) Sylvain Lévi, BEFEO V, p. 286ff; Étienne Lamotte, *Histoire du bouddhisme indien*, 607–610; Uv XXVI (*Nirvānavarga*) 16–19, *Udānavargavivaraṇa* (Balk) II, 707.8ff; Franz Bernhard, ‘Zur Entstehung einer Dhāraṇī’, ZDMG; Jens Braarvig, ‘Bhavya on Mantras: Apologetic Endeavors on Behalf of the Mahāyāna’, in *Aspects of Buddhism: Proceedings of the International Seminar on Buddhist Studies, Liv, 25 June 1994, Studia Indologiczne 4*, Warsaw University: Oriental Institute (1997), 31–39. Bernhard, *Udānavarga*, I, 323, n. 2, 325, n. 1 gives a lists of sources in Chinese which contains the transcribed phrases. For a detailed discussion in Japanese, see Ryūjō Yamada, ‘Sōgya no iminroku ni tai-suru dendō (The Buddhist Missionary to Mleccha in early Sangha)’, *Journal of Indian and Buddhist Studies*, Vol. II, no. 1, Tokyo, September 1953, 85–91. I am grateful to Nobumi Iyanaga for making an abstract of the article for me.
81. *Mimāṃsākaustubha* of Khaṇḍadeva, cited in Madhav M. Deshpande, ‘Mimāṃsā on the Linguistic Usage of the Mlecchas as an Aid to Vedic Interpretation’, in Grant Parker and Carla M. Sinopoli (ed.), *Ancient India in Its Wider World*, Ann Arbor: Center for South and Southeast Asian Studies, The University of Michigan, 2008, 135 (full article, 129–142).
82. There are many books and essays on India at the time of the Buddha. See most recently Kumkum Roy, ‘Society at the Time of the Buddha’, in Rebecca Redwood French and Mark A. Nathan (ed.), *Buddhism and Law: An Introduction*, New York: Cambridge University Press, 2014, 31–45.

83. Jawaharlal Nehru, *The Discovery of India*, New Delhi: Penguin Books, 2004 (first published The Signet Press, Calcutta, 1946), 132–133.
84. For the distinction between the historical and the historicist Buddhas, see Peter Skilling, 'La vie du Bouddha: Traditions et Histoire', *Religions et Histoire* 8 (mai-juin 2006), 18–23. For Buddhism and science, see Donald S. Lopez, Jr., *The Scientific Buddha: His Short and Happy Life*, New Haven and London: Yale University Press, 2012.
85. See Peter Skilling, 'Who Invented Dependent Arising? A Short Sūtra from the *Nidānasamyukta*.' In *Saddharmāmṛtam. Festschrift für Jens-Uwe Hartmann zum 65. Geburtstag*. Edited by Oliver von Criegen, Gudrun Melzer, and Johannes Schneider. Vienna: Arbeitskreis für Tibetische und Buddhistische Studien (WSTB 93), 2018, 441–458.
86. *Nidānasamyukta*, Sūtra 5. See also Gregory Bongard-Levin, Daniel Boucher, Takamichi Fukita, and Klaus Wille, 'The Nagaropamasūtra: An Apotropaic Text from the Samyuktāgama, A Transliteration, Reconstruction, and Translation of the Central Asian Sanskrit Manuscripts', in *Sanskrit-Texte aus dem buddhistischen Kanon: Neuentdeckungen und Neueditionen III* (Sanskrit-Wörterbuch der buddhistischen Texte aus den Turfan-Funden, Beiheft 6), Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1996; for the Sanskrit of the *Pravrajāvastu* see Claus Vogel and Klaus Wille, *Samgharakṣitāvādāna*, in *Sanskrit-Texte aus dem buddhistischen Kanon: Neuentdeckungen und Neueditionen III* (as above), 257, penult.–265.11; for Tibetan of the *Pravrajāvastu*, see Helmut Eimer, *Rab tu 'byuñ ba'i gzi*, Wiesbaden: Otto Harrassowitz, 1983, II, 281.4–289 (spoken by Samgharakṣita as the *grog khyer lta bu'i mdo*). For a commentary, see Kalyāṇamitra's *Vinayavastu-ṭīkā*, in The Tibetan Tripitaka, Peking Edition, kept in the Library of the Otani University, Kyoto, reprinted under the Supervision of the Otani University, Kyoto, edited by Daisetz T.S. Suzuki, Bstan-ḥgyur, Mdo-ḥgrel, Ḥdul-ba'i ḥgrel-pa III, Vol. 122, Tokyo–Kyoto, Tibetan Tripitaka Research Institute, 1957, 'Dul ba'i 'grel pa, dzu, 342a5 257.1.5 foll.
87. *dāpavatiṅ*, a problematic word: see note 8 at Bongard-Levin et al. (who translate 'radiant'), p. 94.
88. *Nidānasamyukta*, Sūtra 11.6. For the passage see *Samghabhedavastu I*, 159, and *Bimbisārapratyudamana-mahāsūtra*, § 4.14–15.
89. *yaḥ pratītyasamutpādaḥ, śūnyatāṃ tām pracakṣmahe; sā prajñaptir upādāya pratīpat saiva madhyamā*: That which is conditioned arising, that we declare to be emptiness. Emptiness is a relational designation, and it is precisely the middle way. Nāgārjuna, *Mūlamadhyamakārikā*, 24:18.
90. *apratītyasamutpanno dharmāḥ kaścīn na vidyate; yasmāt tasmād aśūnyo hi dharmāḥ kaścīn na vidyate*. Nāgārjuna, *Mūlamadhyamakārikā*, 24:19.
91. Bhikkhu Anālayo sees a close relation between 'the tendency in the Abhidharma traditions to attempt a comprehensive coverage of all relevant items' and the belief that the Buddha's 'awakening involved his gain of omniscient knowledge': see Anālayo, *The Dawn of Abhidharma*, Hamburg: Hamburg University Press, 2014 (Hamburg Buddhist Studies 2), 117–127. With regard to the *Paṭṭhāna*, the largest and in many sense most complex book of the Pali Abhidhamma, Pyi Phyo Kyaw remarks that 'Drawing upon the commentaries, Burmese Buddhists believe that only the Buddha's omniscient wisdom (*sabbāññuta-nāṇa*) can fully comprehend and understand the profound, interdependent causal relationships described in the *Paṭṭhāna*. Therefore, the *Paṭṭhāna* is believed to be the embodiment of the Buddha's omniscience by Burmese Buddhists': Pyi Phyo Kyaw, *Paṭṭhāna (Conditional Relations) in Burmese Buddhism*, Thesis submitted for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), King's College London (University of London), 2014, p. 109.
92. See Peter Skilling, 'Birchbark, Bodhisattvas, and Bhānakas: Writing materials in *Buddhist North India*', in Nalini Balbir and Maria Szuppe (ed.), *Eurasian Studies XII* (2014): Lecteurs et copistes dans les traditions manuscrites iraniennes, et centrasiatiques/Scriptes and Readers in Iranian, Indian and Central Asian Manuscript Traditions, (Istituto per l'Oriente-Roma – Orientalisches Institut der Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg, Journal for Balkan, Eastern Mediterranean, Anatolian, Caucasian, Middle Eastern, Iranian and Central Asian Studies), 499–521.